

Ship Tracking and Imaging using DVB-S Signals and a Low-Cost Passive Receiver System

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Abstract

Satellites are generally very well suited as a platform for SAR applications. The ability to acquire data about any location on Earth makes satellite-based radars indispensable for cartography, hydrology, disaster response, or oceanography. But continuous observation of small local areas cannot be satisfied by the current satellite programs. In contrast to traditional SAR applications, this work is concerned with using geostationary satellites as a ubiquitous illuminator for a low-cost ground-based passive radar system for detecting, tracking, and imaging ships. Experimental data will be used to verify the suitability of our system for such applications.

1 Introduction

The utilization of readily available sources for SAR imaging is becoming increasingly affordable. For instance, our department has already demonstrated that terrestrial signals such as DVB-T can be used in a passive configuration for bistatic SAR imaging [1].

Using DVB-S (Digital Video Broadcasting - Satellite) signals, for the first time the SAR research group at Politecnico di Milano has successfully used a Hotbird satellite from Eutelsat as a source for SAR imaging with a stationary receiver on the ground [2].

Another application to use these freely available, inexpensive and reliable satellites is the tracking of moving objects with a passive receiving system. In this case, the synthetic aperture is achieved through the movement of the objects rather than the movement of the illuminator. To evaluate the feasibility, the decision was made to utilize ships for tracking due to their high backscatter. One implementation of this is realized in [3] by Fraunhofer FHR in the form of a traditional turntable experiment using Astra 1N as the illuminator. In [4], Fraunhofer FHR introduces the SABBIA system, which is a DVB-S-based passive radar operating in the Ku-band. Its results for maritime surveillance applications are presented in [5]. As a further implementation, the DVB-S signal was used for ship detection near the coast in conjunction with DVB-T signals [6]. In [7], the same author published an article on passive polarimetric ISAR for the imaging of ship targets.

2 The Configuration

2.1 Transmitter: Geostationary Satellite

Since geostationary satellites are positioned directly above the equator, the number of possible azimuth angles of the transmitter to the scene is limited. If the scene an-

tenna is not aligned with the line of sight, the size of the resolution cell increases.

In our case, the receiving system is limited to a frequency range from 11.8 GHz to 12.7 GHz, so the selected satellite should operate at the highest possible power in this frequency band. In our experiments, the DVB-S signal from a geostationary satellite is used as signal source for generating SAR images. Therefore, it is important to test this signal for its suitability for radar applications by investigating its properties and ambiguity function. In this type of modulation, the data is scrambled by a pseudo-random noise sequence, ensuring a uniform energy distribution over the entire bandwidth, independent of the content. Such a pseudo-random signal is atypical for radar applications. In addition, the equivalent isotropic radiated power (EIRP) and the signal bandwidth are significantly lower than those of conventional high-resolution SAR satellites.

2.2 The Receiver System

The system used in the experiments consists of two receiving channels, which allows the simultaneous acquisition of the signal from the geostationary satellite and the reflections from the moving targets. As shown in Fig. 1, an offset parabolic antenna with a diameter of 100 cm is used for the direct channel. The reflection channel is equipped with a 23 dBi horn antenna. The low-noise block down converters (LNBs) are mounted directly on the antennas and are synchronized by an external 10 MHz reference signal. A fixed LO frequency of 11.3 GHz is used.

The core component of the low-cost receiver system is the USRP B210 SDR, which covers RF frequencies from 70 MHz to 6 GHz. It can operate with a real-time bandwidth of up to 30 MHz for two receive channels. A detailed description of the system is given in [8, 9].

Usually, the bandwidth of a transponder for broadcasting TV channels is in the range of 22 MHz-36 MHz. Due

to the limitation of our recording system we can only use the signals of a single transponder.

3 Experiments and Results

3.1 Experimental Setup

To obtain bistatic radar data, a measurement system was mounted on a hill in *Monheim am Rhein* to monitor the passage of ships (Fig. 1). The transmitting satellite needs to meet specific criteria, including transmitting power, coverage area, an appropriate frequency band, and available bandwidth. In addition, the azimuth angle, i.e. the horizontal angle at which the satellite is seen from the site in Monheim am Rhein, should be orthogonal to the ship's direction of travel.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of the ISAR experiment in Monheim on the Rhine.

Based on these requirements, the Astra 2E satellite is used as illuminator for the ISAR experiments. The center frequency of the used transponder is 11.934 GHz and the polarization of the DVB-S signal is vertical with a bandwidth of 27.5 MHz. Fig. 2 shows the spectral density of the transponder used. The shape is almost rectangular.

Figure 2: Spectral density of the direct signal.

The geometry of the image acquisition is shown in Fig. 3. Here, the direct antenna is pointed at the Astra

satellite and the scene antenna is pointed towards the ship. The motion of the ship is used to form the synthetic aperture; The relative movement of the satellite during the recording time of 60 seconds is so small that it does not contribute significantly to the synthetic aperture.

Figure 3: Geometry of data acquisition.

The direct signal and the received scene echo are sampled continuously at a rate of 30 MHz and then divided into individual (range) pulses to obtain the 2D SAR raw data. The pulse compression was realized as matched filter, using the direct signal of the satellite.

For the azimuth processing, the required parameters are estimated from the corresponding spectrograms. However, the backscatterer spectrum is location-variant, so a specific azimuth filter must be determined for each ship depending on range and speed to correct the Doppler response.

3.2 Results

Several experiments were carried out on different days, in this manuscript two results are shown as examples: one with a small ship and one using a long ship as a target. The passing police ship *Ruhr* represents the class of small ships. According to the analysis of the recorded AIS (Automatic Identification System) signal, the boat has a length of 25 m and was traveling at 5 knots at the time of recording.

Fig. 4(a) illustrates the pulse compressed image in range direction (from top to bottom) along with the corresponding recording time. In each experiment, the bank zones situated 50 meters and 390 meters from the measurement setup are detectable as areas of stable reflection intensity over the entire recording period. Looking at a range of 350 m, the return of the ship can be seen clearly. It extends over a period of 25 s.

Forming a spectrogram from this line of range bins (see Fig. 5), the bistatic Doppler response is obtained. It can be seen that the ship enters the beam of the antenna from second 25 having a Doppler frequency of 20 Hz. In the further course the ship passes the measuring system. After second 30 (Doppler frequency of 10 Hz) the Doppler frequency decrease almost linearly to -25 Hz. This time segment is used for focusing.

Figure 4: (a) Intensity plot of *Ruhr* before focusing. (b) Intensity plot of *Ruhr* after focusing.

Figure 5: Spectrogram of the ship returns.

From the mean Doppler history – with the estimated parameters azimuth chirp rate k_{az} and the aperture duration $\delta\tau$ – the compression filter is derived, which is subsequently applied to the pulse-compressed image (Fig. 4 (a)). Azimuth compression compensates these reflected signals from different directions of incidence with respect to the receiver and the resulting Doppler response.

After estimating the mean azimuth relative velocity, the result is plotted in range and azimuth spatial coordinates to compare the ship length to the actual length. The focusing result (see. Fig. 4 (b)) of the signal shows that the parameter k_{az} was chosen correctly. It gives improved resolution in azimuth, allowing more precise identification of ships.

To estimate the velocity v of the ship and consequently its length, the known relation between Doppler frequency width B_{az} and velocity v can be used. Since this is a bistatic constellation, it should be noted that the phase gradient arises only during the return path of the signal. This means that the equation corresponds to half the value of the monostatic bandwidth:

$$B_{az} = \frac{2v}{\lambda} \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right). \quad (1)$$

φ is the antenna aperture angle of the scene antenna

(20°) and λ signifies the wavelength of the used DVB-S transponder (2.51 cm). The Doppler bandwidth B_{az} can be estimated from the spectrogram (Fig. 5) to be about 36.5 Hz. After rearranging Eq. 1 to v , a ship speed of 5.21 kn is obtained. This corresponds approximately to the actual value. To determine the ship length, first the time period in which the ship is visible in the focused image is determined from Fig. 4 (b) and multiplied by the calculated velocity v . This results in a ship length of approx. 24 m, which is very close to the actual ship length.

3.2.1 Second experiment

In another experiment, the signal echos were captured from the cargo ship *Zwarte Zee* (illustrated in Fig. 6), which was sailing upstream at a speed of 5.5 knots. The ship has a length of 80 m, with a width of 9 m. Again, the recording was made continuously for 60 s at a sampling rate of 30 MHz. This time the data was reshaped so that the PRF of the individual range pulses was 50 Hz, which was sufficient for this experiment. The range profiles over azimuth time can be seen in Fig. 7 (a). It was present within the antenna beam for over 40 s.

Figure 6: Photograph of the *Zwarte Zee*.

In the spectrogram (see Fig. 7 (b)), it can be observed that, in contrast to the small ship, the radar signal in this case is reflected to the receiver from different directions. However, the instantaneous frequency decreases linearly in the same way, which indicates a constant speed of the

Figure 7: (a) Intensity plot of *Zwarte Zee* after pulse compression. (b) Spectrogram of *Zwarte Zee*.

target. In this experiment, the azimuth focusing was carried out with an ω - k processor, neglecting a possible rotation of the ship. By estimating the speed and distance of the ship and receiver, a focused ISAR image is obtained (Fig. 8). The dimensions of the ship can be determined with high accuracy from the processing results.

Figure 8: Zoom in of *Zwarte Zee* processing result using ω - k algorithm.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, the feasibility of passive radar with geostationary satellites for ISAR applications was successfully demonstrated with a low-cost measurement system. This shows the potential of geostationary satellites as effective illuminators, despite the low power density of the transmitted signal on Earth's surface. The pass-by of different ships with different system parameters was observed and analyzed. It was also shown that focusing in azimuth can be easily implemented using parameters derived from the spectrogram. In principle, the Doppler response can be corrected by a chirp with an azimuth sweep rate k_{az} .

However, due to the small width of the vessels in the range direction of the SAR image, a simplified bistatic ω -

k processor leads to good focusing results. With a channel bandwidth of 30 MHz, no significant differences can be seen in the ISAR images processed with the different methods, as the resolution is of the same order of the ship's width and so the azimuth correction only has to be carried out in a few azimuth lines. The ship dimensions or speed determined from the intermediate or final image products closely match the actual values.

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